

POLITICAL SCIENCES

NATIONAL AND POPULAR MODELS IN CARDENISMO: AN ANALYSIS FROM THE WORK OF FERNANDO BENÍTEZ

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the national and popular models that were developed during Cardenismo in Mexico, taking as a framework of reference the work of the Mexican historian Fernando Benítez. His in-depth analysis of national and popular models in Latin America during the first half of the 20th century provides a solid basis for understanding the characteristics and impact of these initiatives in the Mexican context. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of Cardenismo and its role in the history of Mexico and Latin America. By analyzing national and popular models from the perspective of Fernando Benítez, a critical and nuanced vision of this crucial period is offered. We propose to analyze the national and popular models implemented during Cardenismo, evaluate the impact of these models on Mexican society, understand Fernando Benítez's critical perspective on Cardenismo, and extract valuable lessons for today. The research is based on a critical analysis and textual of Benítez's work, complemented with relevant historical sources. A qualitative approach is used to interpret the data and draw significant conclusions about the national and popular models in Cardenismo. The first findings show that after his arrival to the presidency in 1934 he marked a turning point in the history of Mexico. Cárdenas undertook a program of radical reforms that sought to redistribute wealth and social justice. Conclusions The national and popular models of Cardenismo were characterized by their search for a more just and egalitarian society, where the State played a central role in promoting economic and social development.

Keywords: Latin America, State, economy, equality, society.

Introduction

"...The myth of Cárdenas is linked to the history of Mexico. It is a symbol of social justice that is inserted in a broader symbolic universe from which it derives meaning: the Mexican Revolution. This means the beginning of a new era that puts an end to exploitation, which makes equality, justice and democracy possible. He inaugurates a millenarian promise of common good and his instrument is Lázaro Cárdenas..."

Verónica Vázquez Mantecón¹

"...I think justice has not been done. In his time he was accused of being a communist, and now young historians accuse him precisely for not having been one and label him populist, Bonapartist and even fascist..."

Fernando Benítez²

In this study, we analyze the national and popular models that developed during the Cardenismo, using the work of Fernando Benítez as a framework of reference, the Mexican historian provides us with a deep analysis of the national and popular models that emerged in Latin America during the first half of the 20th century. National and popular models emerged as a response to the crisis of capitalism and imperialism that plagued Latin America in the 1930s. These models sought to build more just and egalitarian societies, where the State played a fundamental role in promoting economic and social development. The main objectives of the research are: to analyze the national and popular models implemented in Cardenismo, evaluate the impact of these models in Mexican society, understand Fernando Benítez's³ critical perspective on Cardenismo and extract valuable lessons for today. The

¹ Vázquez Mantecón, Verónica. (2009). Lázaro Cárdenas en la memoria colectiva. *Política y cultura*, (31), 183-209, página 186. Recuperado en 17 de junio de 2024, de http://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0188-77422009000100010&lng=es&tlng=es.

² Benítez, Fernando. (1978). *Lázaro Cárdenas y la Revolución Mexicana*. El Cardenismo. Tomo III. México: FCE. Prologo p.3

³ Fernando Benítez (Ciudad de México, México, 1912). Periodista, narrador, autor de teatro; se inició en el periodismo en 1934. Fue director del diario *El Nacional* (1947-1948) y de los suplementos culturales de *Novedades* (1949-1961), *¡Siempre!* (1962-1971), *Unomásuno* (1977-1986) y *La Jornada* (1987-1988). Ha sido profesor de la Facultad de Ciencias Políticas de la Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, presidente del

*Pen Club y diplomático. Sus obras, relacionadas con la literatura, la historia, la política y la antropología, le valieron múltiples reconocimientos, entre los cuales sobresale el Premio Nacional de Lingüística y Literatura (1978), el Premio Nacional de Antropología (1980), el Premio Nacional de Periodismo (1988) y la presea Belisario Domínguez (1991) que el Senado de la República otorga a los ciudadanos que con su obra cultural y política sirven al país. Fondo de Cultura Económica ha editado de este autor *Viaje al centro de México* (1975), *Lázaro Cárdenas y la Revolución Mexicana I. El porfirismo* (1977), *Lázaro Cárdenas y la Revolución Mexicana II. El caudillismo* (1977) y *Lázaro Cárdenas y la Revolución Mexicana III. El Cardenismo* (1978), disponible: Fondo de Cultura Económica 1934-2024 <https://fce.com.ar/autores/fernando-benitez/>*

research is based on a critical and textual analysis of Benítez's work, complemented with historical sources. Lázaro Cárdenas, emblematic figure of the Mexican Revolution and President of Mexico between 1934 and 1940, stands as a titan of national history. His life, marked by an unwavering commitment to the Mexican people, is divided into three stages: his military period and as a public official until 1934, his presidency itself whose axis is social transformation, and his last 30 years dedicated to the defense of Her ideals. From his early participation in the Revolution in 1913, Cárdenas demonstrated his mettle and vocation for service. His rise in the military ranks led him to occupy relevant positions. As governor of Michoacán from 1928 to 1932, he promoted an ambitious agrarian reform and laid the foundations for his future presidency.

Investigation

In his work "Lázaro Cárdenas and the Mexican Revolution. El Cardenismo", the Mexican historian and journalist Fernando Benítez offers an in-depth analysis of the national and popular models that were developed in Mexico during the six-year term of President Lázaro Cárdenas (1934-1940). Benítez portrays the challenges and achievements of this crucial period in the country's history, highlighting the importance of popular participation and the search for national autonomy as fundamental pillars of these models. The study of national and popular models in the context of Cardenismo is of great relevance for various reasons. Firstly, it allows us to understand the historical context in which these models were created, marked by the global economic crisis, the rise of nationalist movements and the fight for social justice in Latin America. Second, he offers perspectives on the strategies implemented by the Cárdenas government to boost the national economy, redistribute wealth, and strengthen the country's sovereignty. Finally, it allows us to evaluate the impact of these models on Mexican society, considering both their achievements and their limitations.

"...Cárdenas will not be understood outside the framework of the Mexican Revolution. Executor of the always delayed Constitution of 1917, he demonstrated that it was possible to change the course of history by taking care above all of the enormous marginalized mass of Indians, peasants and workers, but a country like ours cannot radically change in six years... he refused the not at all remote possibility of being re-elected, and, when he handed over command to General Manuel Ávila Camacho, he promised never to intervene in active politics, a promise to which he remained faithful until his death..."⁴.

In 1935, Yucatán was practically an island with limited transportation connections, mainly two steamships that traveled between Veracruz and Progreso, from where henequen was exported to the United States. Since 1920, the situation had not improved much. The "divine caste" still considered themselves experts in henequen, despite advances in other places such as Kenya and Tanganyika, where superior fibers were produced. In contrast, Yucatecan planters continued to use antiquated methods and obsolete machinery,

selling their product at low prices to American agents who made large profits.

The landowners lived comfortably off the poorly paid work of their laborers, who were no longer forced or physically abused, but worked in very harsh conditions for miserable wages. Yucatán lacked significant industries, with a society divided between rich landowners and a large mass of laborers, with a small middle class made up of professionals and merchants. This social contrast was evident, with the rich living in luxurious residences and the Indians in traditional cabins. The landowners firmly believed in a natural hierarchy of lords and servants, while the Indians, living in extreme poverty, often resorted to alcohol and maintained ancestral practices, reflecting a sad decline compared to their glorious past.

The author adds *"...General Cárdenas had not forgotten the amazing world of Yucatán. "The Revolution," he had said, "wants the agrarian precepts to be firmly fulfilled throughout the country... That the allocations have not been given in Yucatán because the lands affected by the presidential resolution are cultivated with henequen? I tell you, in name of the Revolution, that the lands must be given, so that you yourselves continue cultivating henequen..."⁵.*

Based on what has been said, we analyze and examine the process of agrarian distribution of henequen in Yucatan during his administration, highlighting the objectives he intended to achieve: comply with the agrarian principles of the Mexican Revolution, improve the living conditions of the Mayan peasants and transform the structure socioeconomic of the henequen region; the difficulties of agrarian distribution became evident. opposition from the landowners, who used various delaying and obstructive tactics; inequality in the distribution of land generated ejidos with significant asymmetries in their productivity; With which the results of the agrarian distribution were carried out by distributing 30 thousand hectares of henequen and 450 thousand hectares of vacant land; Likewise, medical assistance was provided to nearly 20 thousand farmers, improving their health and well-being. Dialogue with the author, he presents the criticism made to the agrarian distribution because it was not possible to correct the initial inequality in the distribution of land, persisting asymmetries between ejidos, while the "Henequeneros de Yucatán" program was transformed into an organization bureaucracy controlled by the government, limiting ejidal autonomy. The potential of the peasants for a profound transformation of the henequen industry was partially wasted. The agrarian distribution of henequen in Yucatán was a complex process and full of contrasts. Although it represented progress in terms of social justice, it did not achieve all its goals due to various factors. The critical reading of Benítez's text allows us to understand the difficulties and challenges that agrarian policies faced in post-revolutionary Mexico, offering valuable lessons for future processes of social and economic transformation in rural areas.

The author describes that the national and popular models in Mexico emerged in a historical context marked by the world economic crisis of 1929, which

⁴ Benítez Fernando op.cit., prólogo, pp. 3-4

⁵Ibid., p.44

had a devastating impact on the country. The crisis exacerbated existing social and economic inequalities, generating a climate of popular discontent and strengthening nationalist movements. In this scenario, the Cárdenas government adopted a series of measures aimed at boosting the national economy, redistributing wealth and strengthening the country's sovereignty.

The national and popular models that were developed during Cardenismo were characterized by: emphasis on popular participation, encouraging the active participation of the population in decision-making and the implementation of public policies. In search of national autonomy, measures were implemented to reduce the country's economic and political dependence on foreign powers. Agrarian reform was also promoted by distributing ejido lands to peasants and indigenous communities, which contributed to the redistribution of wealth and the strengthening of the agricultural sector. Likewise, social programs were implemented to improve the living conditions of the population, such as the construction of schools and hospitals, and the promotion of education and public health.

Even key sectors of the economy, such as the oil and electricity industries, were nationalized with the aim of promoting national development. Therefore, there is a debate among historians about whether the oil expropriation carried out by Cárdenas represented a radical change towards socialism in his government; some argue that it did, while others affirm that it did not. Jorge Abelardo Ramos (1968) in this regard adds "...Nothing is more erroneous than identifying nationalizations in an imperialist country with those of a semi-colonial country. In this way, the nationalization of Mexican oil by Cárdenas would have the same meaning as that carried out in imperialist France in the automobile industry in 1946. The latter was due to the deficit of that industry, saved by the imperialist State through generous compensation. But the "nationalized" owners in France were French, not foreigners, and bourgeois France had nothing to fear from them. Nationalization in Mexico, on the contrary, was a defensive act of a revolutionary country against foreign capital..."⁶. By analyzing the differences between the cases of France and Mexico, the author highlights the importance of understanding the motivations and historical context when evaluating these types of policy measures. Nationalizations in imperialist countries respond to internal economic motivations, while in semi-colonial countries they are configured as an act of defense against foreign domination. In the case of Mexico, the nationalization of oil constituted a crucial event to strengthen national sovereignty and control over a strategic resource.

It was interesting to incorporate the vision of Carlos Granés (2023) who analyzes and describes the actions undertaken by Lázaro Cárdenas during his presidency in Mexico, framed in a context of nationalism and search for progress. The agrarian reforms, the expropriation of strategic sectors and the restructuring of

the political party stand out. Cárdenas, convinced of the central role of the State in national development, implemented various reforms. Among them, the creation of collective ejidos and the distribution of land, measures that sought to meet the demands of the peasantry and strengthen the rural economy. In turn, the promotion of economic nationalism was evidenced in the expropriation of the railroads in 1937 and the oil industry in 1938. These actions, with great symbolic and cultural impact, sought to regain control of strategic resources for the country. It is worth highlighting two measures that had a profound impact on Mexican society: the granting of political asylum to León Trotsky and thousands of Spanish refugees fleeing the Civil War, and the restructuring of the National Revolutionary Party (PNR) in 1938, giving rise to the Party of the Mexican Revolution (PRM). The latter, restructured around four sectors (worker, peasant, popular and military), sought to institutionalize the revolution and, at the same time, control the growing working masses.

In the words of Carlos Granés "...*There is nothing more irritating than not understanding the things that happen. American Delirium helped me understand not only the past, but the immediate present of Colombia and the entire continent...*"⁷.

Cárdenas himself, in a 1940 speech, clarified that his government did not seek to make the State the owner of all the means of production, commerce, and property. He acknowledged that some nationalizations and expropriations were carried out, such as oil and railways, but these measures were forced by the actions of the owners or companies themselves. Furthermore, he maintained that his government was not seeking a complete socialist model, but rather responded to the specific needs of the moment and the actions of the economic actors. "...*There is, therefore, in Mexico*", he added, "*a communist government; our Constitution is democratic and liberal with some moderate features of socialism...*"⁸.

The objectives of the national and popular models were diverse, but in general they sought to: promote economic independence: reducing the dependence of Latin American countries on foreign powers through industrialization, agrarian reform and the nationalization of natural resources. As well as achieving social justice: redistributing wealth, improving the living conditions of the popular classes and guaranteeing access to education and health for all. In addition, focusing on strengthening national identity: promoting local culture and traditions, thus building a sense of national unity between different sectors of the population.

After his presidency concluded, Cárdenas remained active in public life, defending his ideals and working on social development projects. However, his efforts were hampered by the resurgence of landlordism and the penetration of foreign capital, which eroded the progress made during his tenure. Despite the diffi-

⁶ Ramos, J. A. (1968). *Historia de la Nación Latinoamericana*. Buenos Aires: Peña Lillo. p.340

⁷ El País. (2023, 6 de diciembre). Carlos Granés, el ensayista del delirio americano. [https://elpais.com/eps/2023-01-](https://elpais.com/eps/2023-01-28/carlos-granes-america-latina-es-un-lugar-impuro-y-la-busqueda-de-la-pureza-ha-sido-su-perdicion.html)

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⁸ Benítez Fernando. Op. cit., p.91

culties, his legacy remains intact: a man of integrity, visionary and deeply committed to the well-being of the Mexican people.

Preliminary Findings

The first findings show that after his arrival to the presidency in 1934 he marked a turning point in the history of Mexico. Cárdenas, imbued with a deep revolutionary spirit, undertook a program of radical reforms that sought to redistribute wealth and social justice. The oil expropriation in 1938, undoubtedly his most transcendental act, symbolized the recovery of control of natural resources for the Mexican people. His government was also characterized by agrarian reform, the creation of institutions such as the National Polytechnic Institute and the National Institute of Anthropology and History, and support for thousands of refugees from the Spanish Civil War.

Initial evidence suggests that the national and popular models of Cardenismo had a significant impact on Mexican society, generating both achievements and challenges. However, these models also generated inequalities and social conflicts.

Conclusions

The text we analyze not only exalts the figure of Cárdenas, but also offers constructive criticism. It points out the system's inability to resolve structural problems in the Mexican countryside, such as the lack of effective support for ejidos and institutional corruption, which has perpetuated poverty and inequality. This criticism, far from diminishing the figure of Cárdenas, strengthens it, by placing him in a complex historical context and by recognizing the difficulties that he faced in his fight for a more just Mexico.

As for the national and popular models developed during Cardenismo, they represented a turning point in the history of Mexico. These models, driven by popular participation and the search for national autonomy, laid the foundations for the social and economic development of the country. However, they also faced challenges and limitations, such as lack of resources, opposition from powerful groups, and the complexity of implementing structural reforms. Despite these difficulties, the legacy of Cardenismo remains valid in the fight

for social justice, equality and national sovereignty in Latin America.

By including Carlos Granés and his work *Delirio Americano* allowed us to observe Cárdenas's strategy to consolidate his political power, which was characterized by a strong Economic Nationalism. Meanwhile, the co-option of popular sectors through unions and organizations became a key tool to maintain social control. In this sense, the PRM, with its sectoral structure, reflected this trend, similar to that observed in other leaders of the time such as Getulio Vargas and Juan Domingo Perón. His legacy continues to be the subject of debate and analysis, but without a doubt, his figure represents a fundamental milestone in the history of Mexico.

It is important to highlight that Fernando Benítez's writings offer a critical vision of national and popular models. The author recognizes his achievements, but also points out his limitations and errors. This critical look is essential to understand the history of Latin America and to build more just and sustainable development models in the immediate present with projection into the future.

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